

Procurement Innovation for Cloud Services in Europe

PICSE Results

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Procurement Innovation for Cloud Services in Europe

TOP FIVE OBJECTIVES

Who is PICSE for?

Stay Tuned!

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Why public research organisations?

A more **flexible and agile procurement process** must be created and implemented to **speed up the uptake of cloud services for the research sector**

Major challenges

1. **Cloud computing is disrupting the way IT resources are provisioned**
2. **In-house resources, publicly funded e-infrastructure and commercial cloud services are not integrated** to provide a seamless environment
3. Current **organisational and financial models are not appropriate** anymore
4. The new way of **procuring cloud services is also a matter of skills and education**
5. **Legal impediments exist**

The consultation process

Gathering use cases and best practices to increase knowledge

<http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.46973>

D3.2 Procurement Best Practices

PICSE Wizard: Cloud service procurement made easy

➤ An easy-to-use web-based service to help **public research organisations** make informed decisions about how to procure cloud services

➤ Who is it for?

Procurement officials

IT managers

Procurement initiators

willing to procure cloud services through a tender procedure

wiz.picse.eu

Wizard - Two main functions

Find the best cloud procurement model

Assess how suitable your current procurement process is for procuring cloud services

wiz.picse.eu

It's time to turn knowledge acquired into concrete actions

October 2014

March 2015
**Cloud procurement
Barriers Report**

June 2015
**Research Procurement
Model**

July 2015
**Procuring cloud
services today**

September 2015
**PICSE Wizard
wiz.picse.eu**

January 2016
**Cloud procurement
best practices for
public sector**

← **CONSULTATION WITH KEY
STAKEHOLDERS** →

wiz.picse.eu
**MAKE YOUR CLOUD
PROCUREMENT EASY:
TRY IT NOW!**

All documents are available at
<http://www.picse.eu/publications/deliverables>

The PICSE Roadmap

It is the major lasting legacy of PICSE

- Provides a **landscape of cloud procurement** in the European public research sector;
- **Makes relevant recommendations regarding procurement of cloud services** for public research organisations in Europe;
- **Provides a guide to cloud procurement**, supported by best practices adopted worldwide
- **Proposes actions within the pillar three of the Digital Single Market Strategy** which focus on maximising the growth potential of the digital economy

Who is it for?

PUBLIC RESEARCH ORGANISATIONS

(the demand-side)

CLOUD SERVICE PROVIDERS

(the supply-side)

POLICY MAKERS

(the regulators)

PICSE Call to Action

Competences and organisational culture

Innovation in procurement and services

Stimulating the research cloud ecosystem

Moving towards commoditisation

Validating the benefits

PICSE Call to Action for PROs

- Build internal competences and share needs & best practices

- Adopt cloud standards & use standard contract templates and SLAs

- Review internal procurement policies & make tenders friendly for agile companies including SMEs

- Encourage innovation and competition

- Engage the industry and manage relationships with multiple suppliers

Implement pay-per-use procedures

Experiment in the cloud through free trials and small pilots

PICSE Call to Action for CSPs

Invest in easy end-user interfaces and in training next generation of researchers

- Engage with demand side to understand the needs of the market.
- Create a working economy between suppliers rather than always competing

Establish transparent cloud pricing within clear and publicly available service descriptions

Offer free, standalone tests

PICSE Call to Action for Policy Makers

Educating buyers and consumers on cloud computing

Establish a cloud chapter in the European Assistance For Innovation Procurement (EAFIP)

Create a unique European catalogue of cloud service providers and related services for science

Enable construction of a bottom-up federated cloud for commodity services

- Use the INFRADEV-04-2016 call to pilot a federated IaaS cloud ecosystem
- Establish calls for joint procurement actions focused on SaaS and PaaS services

PICSE Call to Action

Long-term harmonisation for the Digital Single Market

PICSE Roadmap: a joint collaborative effort

Have your say – Contribute to the PICSE Roadmap on Cloud Service Procurement for Public Research Organisations!

The PICSE Roadmap highlights the existing challenges, barriers and trends in procuring cloud services. In addition it presents a precise Call for Action for the three major stakeholders involved in the cloud procurement process: Public Research Sector Organisations (the demand-side), Cloud Service Providers (the supply-side) and Policy Makers (the regulators). Key themes of the call to action:

**Competences and organisational culture | Innovation in procurement and services | Stimulating the research cloud ecosystem |
Moving towards commoditisation | Validating the benefits**

We are looking for additional contributions to the Roadmap. If you want to contribute you just need to drop us an email at info@picse.eu. All the contributors will become part of the Editorial Team of the PICSE Roadmap. **Take now the chance to have your say!**

Deadline to submit a contribution is 31 March 2016

Become a contributor now!

Submit your request at info@picse.eu

We will give you access to the draft version of the Roadmap so that you can provide your feedback!

Thank you – Questions?

Contact us:

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